

SCIENTIFIC FOUNDATIONS OF PEDAGOGICAL
CONFLICTOLOGY

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Annotation

To understand the science of conflictology, it is necessary to turn to ancient philosophy, within the framework of which an attempt was made to understand the world rationally for the first time. Ancient views on conflict were built on the basis of the philosophical doctrine of contradictions. This article talks about the history of conflictology and its development.

Key words: sociology, society, conflictology, psychology, antic, method.

At present, knowledge about pedagogical conflicts is conditioned by the laws of social development and practice is inextricably linked with the process of reflection and repetition of pedagogical conflicts that occur in pedagogical reality in human thinking. , has a number of unique features that describe the criteria of scientific character, the style of scientific thinking, and the methods of scientific knowledge. The goal of scientific and theoretical knowledge of pedagogical conflicts in the process of modern education and training is to acquire reliable scientific knowledge about them in the pedagogical reality by mastering the methodology of pedagogical conflictology. There is an understanding of the place and importance of pedagogical conflicts in the process of scientific knowledge by the teacher in the real pedagogical reality. The most important criteria of scientific knowledge defined by P.V. Alekseev, A.V. Panin defines as follows:

- logical validity, evidence (giving necessary scientific grounds for the content of knowledge about pedagogical conflict to be true);
- essential direction (aimed at reflecting the essence of the phenomenon of

pedagogical conflict, the laws of its emergence, development, resolution);

- systematic organization of knowledge (regulation of pedagogical conflict based on conscious principles of scientific knowledge, classification in the form of pedagogical conflict theory, its detailed theoretical concept);

- verifiability (referring to scientific observation, practice, scientific logic of studying pedagogical conflict).

Based on the acquired scientific knowledge about pedagogical contradictions, the teacher should prevent and constructively solve them in future pedagogical activities in order to qualitatively harmonize and establish pedagogically appropriate relations between the leading subjects of the pedagogical process. must understand the need. a new humanistic basis. Thus, the teacher's mastery of the methodological foundations of pedagogical conflictology should help to form a methodological culture of scientific thinking on the problem of pedagogical conflicts, "its content includes methodological reflection, scientific reasoning, critical thinking and creative abilities implementation of certain principles, research methods and procedures to organize the process of scientific knowledge of pedagogical conflicts and to develop the ability to anticipate and eliminate them in real pedagogical reality. it should help to develop their scientific pedagogical consciousness in seeing and eliminating them. Scientific pedagogical consciousness in anticipating and eliminating pedagogical conflicts reflects the ability to perceive, understand and understand pedagogical conflicts in order to anticipate and eliminate them in the pedagogical process; The ability to understand oneself, personality, professional role in this process on the basis of ideas, knowledge, relationships based on the study of the nature, characteristics, laws and laws of their emergence, development and resolution in real pedagogical reality. Science methodology is the beginning of reality. It is a doctrine about internal points, building principles, forms, methods, scientific-cognitive activity and change, and forms the theoretical basis of a vital scientific concept. Pedagogical

conflictology methodology means anticipation (prevention) of pedagogical conflicts and practical for the purpose of application, it is necessary to understand a set of theoretical rules about the initial foundations, principles, forms, and methods of scientific and cognitive activity. overcoming (resolving) pedagogical conflicts in real pedagogical reality.

The methodology of pedagogical conflictology is presented in descriptive and prescriptive forms. The descriptive methodology, which reflects the structure of scientific knowledge, the laws of scientific knowledge, serves as a general methodological guide for the future teacher and describes the already completed process of scientific knowledge of pedagogical conflicts. Prescription methodology is manifested in the form of direct normative instructions and rules for the implementation of scientific activity in the process of scientific knowledge of pedagogical conflicts by future teachers, i.e. aimed at regulating scientific activity. The methodology of pedagogical conflictology in practice-oriented knowledge reflects the starting points, structure, functions and methods of scientific research of pedagogical conflicts by teachers. The methodology of pedagogical conflictology is reflected in the relevant theoretical and methodological model. This model describes the structure of the process of scientific knowledge of pedagogical conflicts by teachers, allows to monitor the development of this process through the system of approach principles, research methods and procedures, and to establish external and internal connections between its leading components. Conceptualization of modern methodology proves that it has the function of determining the strategy of scientific knowledge. The main goal of the theoretical and methodological model is to reflect the theoretical and methodological strategy of scientific knowledge of pedagogical conflicts by the teacher, which implies a step-by-step transition from one level of methodological analysis of this phenomenon to another, aimed at the development of methodological culture. scientific thinking on the problem of pedagogical

conflicts.

Lack of preparation of teachers and leaders of educational institutions for conflict management, inability to find optimal ways to manage conflicts in school, prevent and eliminate them, as a rule, has a negative impact on the organization of the educational process at school. is doing. The teaching profession is very important because the development of society depends on it.

Literature

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